

ADDITIONAL FILE 1: Supplemental figures

Figure S1. Protein numbers (diversity) of the different functional types found in the secretomes from different media. (A) Poplar chips. (B) Wheat straw. (C) HAT (glucose) medium (see Additional file 2: Tables S1-S3 for the complete protein lists in each of the secretomes).

Figure S2. Venn diagrams of CAZy (A) and oxidoreductase (B) numbers in secretomes. The numbers of unique and shared proteins in the poplar wood, wheat straw and HAT secretomes are indicated (with percentages of total in parenthesis).